

CrossGov

Coherent & Cross-compliant Ocean Governance for Delivering the EU Green Deal for European Seas

NORTH SEA
BALTIC SEA
MEDITERRANEAN SEA

#crossgovproject
www.crossgov.eu

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Norwegian Institute of Water Research (NIVA)

CrossGov primarily applies methodologies & expertise from social sciences, especially policy sciences and law.

COORDINATOR

Norwegian Institute of Water Research (NIVA) | NORWAY

Norway's foremost interdisciplinary center of expertise for environmental and resource issues related to freshwater and marine ecosystems.

UNIVERSITIES

The University of Eastern Finland (UEF) | FINLAND

Law School Center for Climate Change, Energy and Environmental Law (CCEEL)

Utrecht University (UU) School of Law | THE NETHERLANDS with its Netherlands Institute for the Law of the Sea (NILOS), currently part of the Utrecht Centre for Water, Oceans and Sustainability Law (UCWOSL)

RESEARCH ORGANISATIONS

ACTeon SARL – environment, research & consultancy | FRANCE

Institute for Advanced Sustainability (IASS) | GERMANY

Italian National Research Council, Institute of Marine sciences (CNR-ISMAR) | ITALY

CONSULTANCY COMPANIES

s.Pro - Sustainable Projects GmbH | GERMANY

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MISSION

The project aims to enhance knowledge on how coherence and cross-compliance of marine related policies and legislation affect the ability to realise the EU Green Deal goals and Sustainable Blue Economy.

The goal is to facilitate cross-compliance within and across biodiversity, pollution and climate-related laws and policies and therefore to halt the degradation of the European seas more effectively.

CORE STRENGTHS

Close collaboration with the policymaking community, enabling policymakers to effectively foster environmentally sustainable law and governance that is fit-for-purpose for delivering the societal transformation called for in the Green Deal.

OUTCOMES

Production of co-created knowledge and solutions through fit-for purpose roadmaps and methodological guidelines.

OBJECTIVES

Concretise the various marine-related targets and objectives of the Green Deal and its related policies. The project will develop future-oriented scenarios that visualise coherence and cross-compliance challenges for 2030 in the North Sea, Baltic Sea and Mediterranean Sea regions.

Develop analytical methodological guidelines for the study of coherence and cross-compliance. Based on reviews of existing methodology, the project will develop draft guidelines for assessing coherence and cross-compliance towards several policies, for assessing goal achievement towards the Green Deal and for the critical analysis of science-policy-society interfaces.

Provide end-users with a methodological toolbox. Guidelines will be produced and tested in research and evaluated in dialogue with stakeholders before final versions will be presented as a user-friendly ICT tool to be applied by research- and policymaking communities.

Analyse and explain (in-)coherence of marine EU policies. Deliver analyses and explanations of the horizontal coherence of a broad set of marine EU and international policies and legislation and the vertical coherence of national policies in selected Member States versus these higher-level frameworks, including the Green Deal.

MSFD

MSPD

GREEN DEAL

WFD

ND

Study implementation in practice and the challenges of cross-compliance. The project will provide analyses of potential weaknesses, trade-offs, and underexploited synergies in cross-compliance of marine policies through case studies, focusing on the implementation of Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), Water Framework Directive WFD, Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD) and Nature Directives (ND), and the integration of key Green Deal (GD) objectives into sectoral decisions.

Increase the understanding of the outcomes of decisions. Analyse decisions on policies and regulations as well as their practical implementation to understand to what extent biodiversity, pollution or climate related issues are taken into consideration, and explain the results based on rational input from scientific advice and political processes.

Suggest improved science-policy-society interfaces. Together with relevant policy-making and research communities active in selected policy sectors and case study areas, the project will co-develop proposals as blueprints fit-for-purpose to overcome identified challenges.

Develop guidance as digital roadmaps. Based on the analyses of coherence and implementation in practice, the CrossGov project partners in close collaboration with the Stakeholder Forum and Advisory Board will develop recommendations for better integrated policies towards the implementation of the Green Deal within the three marine regions.